

PACIFIC ISLANDS FORUM

TOWARDS AN EQUITABLE TRANSITION TO LOW CARBON GROWTH

Exploring the potential and limitations of carbon pricing in the Pacific

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Preface

This paper provides an analysis of the potential and limitations of carbon pricing in the Pacific context and was prepared to support the discussions by the Forum Finance and Economic Ministers on the relevance, practicalities, and challenges of carbon pricing in the Pacific.

- Section 1. Executive summary
- Section 2. Objectives and scope of the paper
- Section 3. Methodology
- Section 4. Introduces the concept of carbon pricing
- Section 5. An analytical overview of carbon pricing and the different types of carbon pricing mechanisms that are most relevant to the Pacific
- Section 6. An overview of carbon taxes, the current state and trends of carbon taxes, introduces the Singapore model and outlines key considerations for nation states considering a carbon tax
- Section 7. Discusses carbon markets, provides an overview of ETSs, a discussion of the benefits and challenges of carbon markets and recent developments in the region in relation to carbon markets.
- Section 8. Compares and contrasts carbon taxes and carbon markets by presenting a summary of the pros and cons of both mechanisms
- Section 9. Key recommendations
- Section 10. Conclusions

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Abbreviations

ACCU	Australian Carbon Credit Units
ADB	Asian Development Bank
BAU	Business as usual
CER	Clean Energy Regulator
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
ERF	Emissions Reduction Fund
ERP	Emissions Reduction Plan
ETS	Emissions Trading Scheme
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIZ	German Agency for International Cooperation
GtCO ₂ e	Gigaton of carbon dioxide equivalent
IGO	Intergovernmental Organization
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IMO	International Maritime Organization
NDC	Nationally Determined Contributions
NGO	Non-governmental organization
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PICs	Pacific Island Countries
PIFS	Pacific Island Forum Secretariat
SDG	Sustainability Development Goals
SGD	Singapore Dollar
SIDS	Small Island Development States
SPC	South Pacific Community
tCO ₂ e	Ton of carbon dioxide equivalent
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
REDD+	Reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation
WB	World Bank

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1.0 Executive Summary

1. **Carbon pricing is argued as an effective tool to assist countries achieve their NDCs.** This is because carbon pricing puts a price on carbon emissions and can create a financial cost to emitting carbon and potentially a financial reward for reducing carbon emissions.
2. **Carbon prices range from less than \$US 1 to \$US137 per ton of carbon.** Scandinavian countries such as Sweden have the highest carbon prices in the world. The global average for carbon prices is \$US 3 per ton. The IMF argue that a carbon price of \$75 a ton is needed in order to reduce emissions enough to keep global warming below 2°C.
3. **Carbon pricing is happening everywhere except in the majority of SIDS.** This is primarily because of the costs of implementing carbon pricing and the low carbon footprint of SIDS. Carbon prices should be consistent with a country's carbon footprint. That is, high polluting countries should have high carbon prices. The IMF suggest the following price floors:

Development status	Carbon price floor
High-income	\$US 75
Middle-income	\$US 50
Low-income	\$US 25

4. **The two most common methods of carbon pricing are carbon taxes and emission trading schemes.** Carbon taxes are argued to be the most relevant if carbon pricing is to be implemented by finance ministries. Emissions Trading Schemes are more relevant if implemented by national climate change divisions. New Zealand has an ETS, and Australia uses an Emissions Reductions Fund (ERF).
5. **Regional carbon offset schemes present opportunities for PICs but require the development of institutional frameworks.** The Australian Indo-Pacific Carbon Offset Scheme was launched at the end of 2021 and Fiji and PNG were the first two official partners. The scheme is part of Australia's broader climate mitigation strategy in the region and the scheme can support the Pacific's blue and economy initiatives. The development of institutional and human resource capacity remains an issue and the Australian government, other countries and development partners have offered to provide financial and technical support in these areas.
6. **Carbon pricing, if implemented at a national level will likely increase the cost of living, but COVID and the Ukraine-Russia war have shown that costs will rise, and governments respond accordingly to price increases from exogenous events.** A potential solution to

mitigating inflationary pressure caused by carbon pricing is to use the proceeds from carbon taxes to reduce other taxes or pay dividends to citizens. The decision to implement carbon pricing must be based on sound and reliable data, rigorous modelling and the consideration of the specific circumstances, resources and capabilities of each country.

7. Pacific leaders could advocate for higher carbon prices for high polluting countries.

There is no urgent need for PICs to implement carbon pricing at a national level but there is an urgent need for the biggest emitting countries to implement more effective carbon pricing mechanisms and higher prices in order to keep global temperatures below the 2°C agreed in Paris. The Pacific could use their status as the climate most vulnerable region to advocate for the biggest polluters to adopt higher carbon prices.

2.0 Objective and terms of scope of the study

The objective of the assignment is to develop an analytical/research piece in line with the Forum Economic Ministers Meeting (“FEMM”) directives to examine the potential of carbon pricing mechanisms in the Pacific. The findings and recommendations will provide the necessary briefing materials that will be used by Ministers in the 2022 FEMM. The output will also contribute to the ongoing climate finance discussions and policy framing in the region, particularly in strengthening understanding of how the Pacific can leverage as well as scale-up funding from innovative sources.

The scope of the study involves:

- a) Providing a robust analysis of the range of carbon pricing mechanisms of relevance to Forum members and providing a high-level overview of which mechanisms are likely to impact the Pacific and which might lead to beneficial outcomes;
- b) Conducting a robust analysis of the likely scale of greenhouse gas (“GHG”) emissions from Pacific Forum member countries, and the related potential for establishing a regional carbon market;
- c) Enquiring into any cost incentives or disincentives currently offered by member countries on fossil fuels usage and report on their pricing impacts for identifying opportunities for domestic policy changes that can incentivize shift in behavioural paradigms in member countries;
- d) Undertaking carbon emissions pricing (levy or taxes) scenario analysis and determine the likely revenue impacts as well as economic cost impacts, both direct and indirect, inclusive of assessment on two levels: (i) examining the impacts on Forum member states if a range of scenarios are implemented at the international level; and (ii) how various scenarios be developed at the regional/national level react to the international options on the table to either accommodate or amplify what is being done at the global scale?
- e) Based on scenario analysis, the study makes recommendations on the feasibility or otherwise of imposing carbon pricing mechanisms for Forum Member countries and summarises likely timelines and capacity needs for the development of such opportunities.

3.0 Methodology

The approach to the study involved the following:

- a) Review of literature on carbon pricing focusing on the different approaches, debates, problems, success stories and examples of carbon pricing mechanisms; and
- b) Consulting with stakeholders including staff of the PIFS, government representatives, private sector entrepreneurs, civil society organizations, academics, researchers and other experts. The full list of those engaged is provided in the Appendix.

This report is not without its limitations. The limitations include a lack of views and opinions from some PICs and industry stakeholders. In the planning stage of this report, the team consciously attempted to ensure representation in terms of PICs and sectors. We sent interview requests to various PICs and industries, however, some stakeholders did not reply to our requests. Furthermore, data used for the scenario analysis is limited and dated as these were the only fuel import data that was publicly available.

With regards to the lack of responses from some PICs and industry stakeholders, this could be due to most PICs lacking carbon pricing mechanisms. The responses received, potentially represent the countries and industries leading the way in carbon pricing in the Pacific.

4.0 Introduction

Carbon pricing refers to the intentional factoring of the cost of emitting carbon into the production/supply of a product/service. “Intentionality” is stressed because traditionally the cost of emitting carbon was often ignored as it was seen as an external factor. Carbon pricing is being implemented at various scales, either voluntarily by companies, or by mandate at the national, regional or international level. Those that are implementing carbon pricing are doing so because imposing a price on carbon, creates disincentives for individuals, organisations and countries to consume products and services that increase carbon emissions. Putting a price on carbon is generally expressed as follows:

Price per ton of carbon (CO₂).

Carbon pricing is a new concept in the Pacific and as the countries in the region commit themselves to addressing the threat of climate crisis, the issue is bound to be mainstreamed into development policies. For this reason, robust and context specific research, data and analysis are needed to ensure that carbon pricing policies are beneficial to the local population, non-punitive, equitable, sustainable and effective in terms of achieving the carbon emission targets of the individual PIF countries.

However, a number of challenges need to be dealt with by PIFS, member countries, civil society and stakeholders. These include the diversity of policy, political and economic interests between PIF countries; the competing interests of commercial and other stakeholders and their influence on the regional climate policies; ensuring equity in the carbon pricing system at the national and regional levels; negotiating the gap between national and regional interests; and designing a carbon pricing system which ensures accountability, transparency, due diligence and long-term sustainability.

PIF countries are not all the same when it comes to framing and implementing climate policies. Some countries already have carbon pricing legislations while some are already working on theirs and at the other extreme are those who do not have any process in place. This is where regional cooperation can become useful to ensure that those which have the resources to frame their policies and legislations can provide support for those who do not.

There is no one-size- fits-all approach to carbon pricing and organizations/countries/regions must evaluate their circumstances, resources, development aspirations and carbon emissions goals when determining appropriate carbon pricing mechanisms. Based on the variety of carbon pricing mechanisms, the mixed results experienced by different countries and the need for countries to assess their individual circumstances, the Pacific Island Forum Secretariat

(PIFS) commissioned this paper to assist Finance and Economic Ministers of the Pacific better understand both the potential, limitations and risks of carbon pricing.

To ensure the relevance of the paper to the Pacific region, the paper has been written with significant consultation with relevant stakeholders in the region. These stakeholders included government officials, academics, private sector companies, intergovernmental organizations (IGOs) and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) from a sample of member countries.

5.0 Carbon pricing: An analytical overview

Carbon pricing has been extolled as an effective instrument in transitioning to a low carbon world (OECD, 2021). A carbon price sends a clear signal to prioritize investment in low carbon growth. According to the World Bank Carbon Pricing Dashboard, as of 2021 carbon pricing initiatives around the world cover 11.65 GtCO₂e, representing 21.5% of global Greenhouse Gas emissions (GHG) (The World Bank, 2022). While carbon pricing offers a simple and elegant solution to reducing carbon emissions, there exists a variety of carbon pricing mechanisms whose design, implementation and ultimate success depend on the context of the organizational unit implementing carbon pricing.

The Canadian province of British Columbia was able to implement carbon pricing regimes that have led to reduced carbon emissions, an increase in economic growth and reduction in the cost of certain costs and services. While the Canadian example of British Columbia has generally been seen as an exemplar for carbon pricing, not all countries have had similar experiences of success. For developing countries, in particular, carbon pricing raises concerns over increasing costs of doing business, loss of economic trade, loss of jobs and increasing the cost of living to the most vulnerable in the community.

Carbon pricing can be implemented at different scales. A company can implement its own carbon pricing, and this is known as internal carbon pricing. Companies and sectors are setting their own internal carbon prices as they aim to achieve net zero status (N. Bento & Gianfrate, 2020). Some sectors are also considering implementing their own sector-based carbon price. The International Maritime Organisation (IMO) is considering proposals in their upcoming 2022 meeting to achieve the sector's goal of achieving net zero by 2050. One of the proposals is a Global GHG Shipping levy of \$US 100 per ton of carbon on all international shipping bunker. This proposal was submitted by The Republic of the Marshall Islands (RMI), Solomon Islands, Tonga and Tuvalu in May 2021. Nuttall, Irvin, Newell, and Bordahandy (2021) provide an illustration of how this works in Figure 1 next page:

Figure 1. Illustration of shipping carbon tax (Source: Nuttall et al 2021)

The proposed global shipping levy is an example of a sector-based carbon pricing mechanism. Internal carbon pricing for companies does not necessarily mean increasing the cost of production for the organisation but could be used when making investment decisions which otherwise would not incorporate the cost of pollution (Riedel, Gorbach, & Kost, 2021).

Similar to many large private companies that have implemented internal carbon pricing, countries are also implementing carbon pricing either explicitly or implicitly (Mo et al., 2021). Explicit carbon pricing is enacted by a government mandate (e.g. carbon tax or an ETS) and impose a price based on carbon emissions (World Bank, 2021). Implicit carbon pricing does not directly apply a cost to carbon content but calculates the theoretical carbon price from policy instruments aimed at mitigation policies such as efficiency standards or regulations that mandate the use of low or zero-carbon technologies (ibid).

The most common methods for countries to implement explicit carbon pricing² are carbon taxes, emissions trading scheme (ETS) and emission reductions funds. The World Bank (WB) and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) have been two of the key champions of carbon pricing and have produced a range of useful guidance for policymakers on carbon pricing. The World Bank for instance publishes its annual “State and Trends of Carbon Pricing” and in its latest edition identified the following countries that have implemented or are in the process of implementing carbon taxes or ETSs (See Figure 2):

² From hereafter, we use carbon pricing interchangeably with explicit carbon pricing (unless otherwise stated) for ease of reading and also that explicit carbon pricing is what is meant when carbon pricing is referred to in many publications produced by Intergovernmental organizations.

Figure 2. ETSs and Carbon taxes around the world (Source: World Bank 2021)

From a Pacific perspective, there are two important key points. Firstly, Australia does not have a carbon tax or an ETS but instead has an emissions reductions fund and this mechanism will be discussed later. Secondly, no Small Island Developing State (SIDS) of the Pacific has a carbon pricing mechanism in place. In fact, amongst all the SIDS in the world, only Singapore has a carbon pricing mechanism.

Whether it be a carbon tax or an ETS, it can be complex to establish and can lead to increasing the price of goods and services for most consumers. SIDS are often characterized as developing economies with limited resources and whose institutional capacities are still at nascent stages. The issue of equity is also an important factor as SIDS have the smallest carbon footprint but yet are the most affected from the impacts of carbon pricing. Thus, this raises the political and equity issue of why most SIDS and PICs in particular have to implement carbon pricing mechanisms that might increase costs to businesses which will most likely be passed on to consumers. This is even more pertinent as inflationary pressure is being felt globally due to the supply chain disruptions as a result of COVID-19 (Armantier et al., 2021) and more recently the Russia-Ukraine War (Guénette, Kenworthy, & Wheeler, 2022).

While carbon prices present challenges in terms of implementation and their implications for the economic aspirations and the most vulnerable of PICs, they also can present opportunities. While the potential impact on the poor and the most vulnerable is the main deterrent for PICs, other regions have been able to use funds raised from carbon taxes to reduce other taxes and ease the cost of living for their citizens.

Furthermore, the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) are two of the global champions of carbon pricing and have published a number of reports and policy notes on the subject. The IMF believes that carbon pricing shows serious promise as a tool in the fight against climate change by providing across-the-board incentives to reduce energy use and shift to cleaner fuels. This could be useful for PICs in achieving their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). Ian Parry of the IMF makes the following suggestions with regards to carbon pricing:

- a) Carbon pricing can be readily implemented
- b) Carbon pricing is gaining momentum
- c) Carbon pricing should be part of a comprehensive mitigation strategy
- d) Carbon pricing must be coordinated internationally through a carbon price floor
- e) A pragmatically designed price floor is more promising than other regimes

(Parry, 2021)

Given the World Bank and the IMF's support for carbon pricing, these institutions would be amenable to providing technical assistance in helping establish carbon pricing for PICs, should PICs be interested. However, these must be tailored to the needs, culture and socio-economic realities of the region.

Sections 6 and 7 will discuss the three most common and popular forms of carbon pricing with specific examples of SIDS or countries in the Pacific region.

Box 1: Stakeholder Views on Carbon Pricing

- Given that no PIC has a carbon pricing mechanism, it was understandable that most stakeholders were not familiar with carbon pricing or associated carbon pricing as a carbon tax or as an ETS.
- Stakeholders from RMI were very supportive of the proposal to the IMO on the Global GHG Carbon levy on shipping.
- Stakeholders from Cook Islands were concerned about the GHG Shipping levy and its impact on the cost of living for their people.
- Stakeholders from organizations that regulate prices of goods and services stated that shipping freight costs have increased by approximately 200 to 400% due to supply chain disruptions caused by COVID, fuel is not a price regulated item in Fiji, cost of nearly all goods and services have increased during COVID.
- Stakeholders from all countries mentioned the rising cost of items, especially freight and fuel. Most governments have reduced or removed excise taxes on fuel.

6.0 Carbon taxes

Carbon taxes are the most popular form of carbon pricing mechanism because of their simplicity. According to Parry, Veung, and Heine (2015) carbon taxes is most relevant if carbon pricing is being implemented by a country's ministry of finance whereas an ETS is best implemented through a country's ministry of climate change. As a practical example to illustrate how carbon pricing is implemented through carbon taxes, the case of Singapore will be used as Singapore is a SID and offers some useful lessons from PICs.

Box 2: Singapore Model

Singapore introduced a carbon tax in 2019 at \$SGD 5 per tonne of GHG emissions from 2019 to 2023. Singapore will progressively raise its carbon price to \$SGD 25/ tCO₂e in 2024 and 2025, and \$SGD 45/ tCO₂e in 2026 and 2027 with the goal of reaching \$SGD 80 by 2030. Figure 3 below charts Singapore's ambitious carbon price goal.

Figure 3. Singapore's Carbon Price Goals (2019 to 2030)

Box 2: Singapore Model

Singapore's carbon tax was implemented by its National Climate Change Secretariat (NCCS) established under the Prime Minister's Office. Entities that must pay a carbon tax are those entities that directly emit at least 25,000 tCO₂e of GHG annually and includes six GHG that Singapore reports to the UNFCCC.

Singapore's approach of progressively increasing carbon taxes is a common method as it gives time to both the country and to industries to adjust and plan for the impact of carbon taxation. For the country, it provides an opportunity to implement the mechanisms in terms of the laws, reporting systems, verifications systems and in some cases the revenue recycling systems. The initial period also enables governments to review these systems and make any necessary changes and to evaluate the carbon taxes' impact on national GHG emissions, government revenue, inflation and economic growth.

While carbon taxes will generally reduce national GHG emissions, the risk of carbon taxes is their economic impact. Carbon taxes increase the cost of production to producers, and this could be passed on to the consumer in terms of higher prices of goods and services.

The Singapore model offers a useful template for understanding the technical and practical issues of implementing a carbon tax in the Pacific. Singapore's carbon tax was legislated in its Carbon Pricing Act which requires entities that emit direct GHG emissions equal to or above 2,000 tCO₂e annually to register as a reporting entity and submit an Emissions Report annually. It is important to note that emissions from land-based activities and transport emissions are not covered in the Act. The Emissions Report is an excel spreadsheet where the entity will list the total amount of various fossil fuels combusted by the entity or used in the production of other goods. The excel template will then calculate the emissions for each of the quantities of fossil fuels to determine the total emissions for that entity for the year. This figure will then be multiplied by \$5 to determine the entity's total carbon tax payable for the year. As of 2020, Singapore's carbon tax covered 80% of the country's emissions and generated \$US144 million in revenue. The carbon taxes collected would be used to help Singapore transition to a low emission economy (Singapore Government, 2022).

A carbon tax that is implemented in one country but not in another would make the country implementing the carbon tax less attractive for business. Thus, for the Pacific, an important question could be: should there be a regional carbon tax? And if so, should all PICs impose the same regional carbon tax, or should it vary for each country? This is beyond the scope of this paper and has been suggested as future work that needs to be conducted.

Carbon prices vary around the world with Sweden having the highest carbon price of \$US137 followed by Switzerland with \$US101 (World Bank, 2021). While Singapore’s carbon price is low in comparison to Sweden and Switzerland, other larger economies have similar carbon prices to Singapore, for example, Japan and Mexico’s carbon price is \$US3. The lowest carbon prices are in the countries of Poland and Ukraine at \$US0.07 and \$US0.30 respectively. The impact of carbon prices that are less than a dollar has a negligible impact on the costs to be borne by the consumers. These low carbon prices generate very little government revenue. The point of implementing such low carbon prices is to give time for companies, consumers and the government to adjust to carbon taxes and to progressively increase these carbon taxes over time once an evaluation of the impact of these carbon taxes has been adequately assessed. PICs interested in implementing a carbon tax could set a very low price, for instance it could be less than a dollar per tonne of CO₂ emissions and then slowly increase this price over time. The IMF also suggests that a carbon tax should only be one part of a country’s broader GHG emission mitigation strategy.

Scenario Analysis

To illustrate the potential revenue that could be generated at various carbon prices, the following scenario analysis was conducted based on fuel import data of Fiji from 2009 to 2014

Table 1. Scenario Analysis based on Fiji Fuel Import Data

Year	Net Imports (Litres)	CO ₂ Equivalent Emissions	\$US 0.10	\$US 0.50	\$US 1	\$US 2
2009	594,646,167	1,850,557	185,055	925,278	1,850,557	3,701,114
2010	578,425,876	1,800,079	180,007	900,039	1,800,079	3,600,158
2011	406,656,386	1,265,527	126,552	632,763	1,265,527	2,531,054
2012	406,045,749	1,263,627	126,362	631,813	1,263,626	2,527,253
2013	419,548,721	1,305,649	130,564	652,824	1,305,648	2,611,297
2014	535,781,258	1,667,368	166,736	833,683	1,667,367	3,334,735

There are two caveats in the above analysis, firstly, the years used were the only years that were available from the SPC Pacific Data hub website as such the analysis is dated. Secondly, for simplicity purposes, the analysis used a weighted average net caloric factor to convert the fuel quantities into equivalent CO₂ emissions. The analysis above is only meant to be illustrative and provide some indication as to the potential revenue that could be generated at various carbon prices. Countries that are considering implementing a carbon tax could perform similar calculations and can use up-to-date fuel import data and use specific caloric factors for different types of fuel.

While the analysis in Table 1 shows potential revenue at various carbon price points, it is important to note that the main intention of imposing a carbon tax is not to generate additional revenue for the government, rather the revenue collected is generally used to either invest in low emission technologies or redirected to low to middle-income households to reduce the inflationary impact of carbon taxes. Canada is an example of a country that recycled revenue collected from carbon taxes in the form of citizen dividends and reduced other taxes. While revenue recycling could be appealing, especially given the high inflation currently being experienced by PICs, there needs to be appropriate systems in place, citizens on low incomes have bank accounts and are registered in the national tax system.

Box 3: Stakeholder Views on Carbon Taxes

- There was a general lack of appetite for carbon taxes by most stakeholders given the surging prices of fuel and freight which has increased the price of most goods and services in the Pacific.
- The suggestion of revenue recycling received mixed results with some stakeholders feeling that such a system could be administratively burdensome for some PICs.
- A proposal to the IMO for an International GHG Shipping levy of \$US100 per ton of carbon has been submitted by RMI, Solomon Islands, Tonga and Tuvalu. This is an example of a sector-based carbon levy and stakeholders from RMI state that if the levy is approved that PICs are in a strong position to benefit in terms of accessing the funds that would be created from levy.
- Stakeholders from Cook Islands believe that such a levy would increase the cost of living for their citizens and were less supportive of this initiative.

7.0 Emissions Trading Schemes

While carbon taxes are a punitive measure, emissions trading schemes (ETSs) are argued to provide greater incentives for companies to reduce their carbon emissions. ETS are highly complex and poorly understood and it is beyond the scope of this paper to fully explain how an ETS works. For the sake of brevity, the key features of an ETS are a system where entities can trade carbon in a carbon market. Companies that pollute more have to buy more permits to pollute and companies that are able to pollute less can sell credits to companies. The price of these carbon credits is determined by the forces of supply and demand. The European Union (EU) has the largest ETS as it covers the European Union. New Zealand is the only Pacific country that has an ETS.

Many of the stakeholders consulted with have a general appetite for ETS. A few PICs such as PNG, Solomon Islands, Vanuatu and Fiji participate in jurisdictional and voluntary carbon markets. Examples of jurisdictional carbon markets include REDD+ (Reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation) which is an initiative of the UNFCCC and is supported by SPC and the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ).

While countries that participate in a national or regional ETS must purchase credits in order to emit carbon, voluntary carbon markets are for carbon emitters that have voluntarily chosen to offset their emissions by purchasing carbon credits from projects targeted at removing or reducing GHG from the atmosphere. Many corporations have pledged to move to net zero due to increasing shareholder pressure and growing public awareness of climate risks. Corporations and investors are thus seeking to purchase high quality and accredited carbon credits and the Pacific is being perceived as a prime destination as a premium seller of carbon credits. However, the challenge relates to a) institutional and legislative frameworks and b) technical skills and capacities c) policies and frameworks d) data recording and e) the cost of accrediting carbon abatement projects.

The most common form of carbon credits sold by PICs are based on the preservation or the growth of forests. One of the key challenges is on establishing ownership rights of the land. This is particularly problematic in countries like PNG, Solomon Islands and Vanuatu where ownership of land are highly contestable . This is less of an issue in Fiji which has a clearly defined and codified system of land ownership. In the 2021 Fiji Climate Change Act, Part 10 specifically relates to “Carbon Sequestration Property Rights and Emissions Reduction Projects, Programmes and Activities”. These sections cover the recognition of property rights, the registration of carbon sequestration property rights, Fiji’s REDD+ policy and Fiji’s Emissions Reduction Methodologies.

Stakeholders from Fiji who have experience with participating in carbon markets stated that when Fiji participated in the international carbon market the price for Fiji’s carbon credits was too low especially when the price of engaging international consultants to accredit these projects were exorbitant. Ultimately, many projects that were identified for carbon markets were abandoned due to the low price of carbon credits on the international market and the high costs of accreditation. Stakeholders from Fiji stated that if PICs were to participate in a carbon market that it should be a regional carbon market and stated that there has been interest from countries such as Cook Islands and Samoa to work with Fiji and to work with large countries such as Australia and New Zealand. According to Fiji, Australia has shown the greatest interest in working with Fiji in terms of buying carbon credits.

Box 3: Australia’s ERF

Australia does not have an ETS but instead uses an Emissions Reduction Fund (ERF). The ERF is an offset scheme that will buy Australian Carbon Credit Units (ACCUs) from projects that store or remove carbon from the atmosphere. The fund provides an incentive for businesses to invest in projects that reduce carbon emissions and in order to receive funding, these projects must be registered by the administering authority: The Clean Energy Regulator (CER). Once projects are registered, scheme participants enter an auction process where contracts are established and after an audit, participants earn an ACCU that can be either sold to the government or to the secondary market. As of the 4th of March, 2022, the Australian government has allocated \$AU 4.5 billion to the ERF and has entered into contracts to purchase around 230 million tonnes of emissions abatement (Mazengarb, 2022). Figure 4 below illustrates the mechanics of the ERF.

1. ERF project registered with the Clean Energy Regulator (CER) and project established.
2. The scheme participant bids at a CER auction and wins a contract with the Government.
3. The scheme participant audits the project, submits reports to the CER and then receives ACCUs.
- 4a. ACCUs are provided to the Government. Payment is made to the project owner.
- 4b. ACCUs can also be sold on the secondary or voluntary carbon market.

Figure 4. How the ERF works? (Source: ClimateChangeAuthority Australia)

In 2021, the Australian government has established the Indo-Pacific Carbon Offsets Scheme which is a regional carbon market for offset trading. The Australian government has committed \$AU 104 million to the scheme and states that it will run until 2031. The principles guiding the scheme are:

- a) Transparent and inclusive governance
- b) Aligned with the Paris Agreement and United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
- c) Responsibility and cooperation amongst parties
- d) High-integrity Units

Source: (Australian Government, 2022b)

On the 5th of November 2021, Fiji and Papua New Guinea became the first international scheme partners (Australian Government, 2022a). The Australian government will support partner countries to establish national climate policy frameworks, carbon accounting and reporting capacity and a pipeline of carbon offsetting projects.

On 16 May 2022, the New Zealand government announced its establishment of an Emissions Reduction Plan (ERP) which will complement their existing ETS. While sharing similar features with Australia's ERF, the key difference for the Pacific is that New Zealand's ERP is focused only on its domestic carbon offset market and does not allow the purchase of offshore carbon credits. Given the recency of this announcement, the New Zealand government could consider amending this policy. As stated by one stakeholder, historically New Zealand has allowed the purchase of offshore carbon credits and if they do allow this in the new scheme then the Pacific should be given priority.

Box 4: Stakeholder Views on Carbon Markets

- Carbon markets, both jurisdictional and voluntary, are growing and there is keen interest in purchasing carbon credits from the Pacific.
- A stakeholder stated that due to PICs' small carbon footprint and abundance of carbon sinks, that PICs should be sellers of carbon credits and not buyers.
- Stakeholders from Fiji have made significant progress in developing their legislative frameworks to facilitate the creation and registration of carbon credits in Fiji.
- Stakeholders from Fiji, based on their past experience, stated that selling carbon credits to a smaller market would fetch higher prices than on a larger international market.
- Stakeholders also noted that the cost of accrediting carbon abatement/sequestration projects is quite high and often outweighs the financial returns.

8.0 Carbon Taxes vs Carbon Markets

The literature on carbon taxes vs ETS is quite mixed. The general comparison is that carbon taxes are the “stick” approach and that ETS uses a more “carrot” approach. The literature on carbon taxes and ETS in developing economies is sparse with literature on SIDS even more scarce. The literature on carbon taxes focuses more on arguing why carbon taxes should be imposed on the biggest polluting countries or sectors and this makes sense and explains why few literature exists on carbon taxes on SIDS whose carbon emissions are paltry in comparison to larger countries. ETS are very complex, and no SIDS has its own ETS. It is argued for SIDS to be sellers of carbon credits to national emissions reductions fund (as in the case of Australia) or to the voluntary carbon markets.

Based on the available literature, recent government announcements and stakeholder consultations, the following tables present a summary of the pros and cons of carbon taxes vs carbon markets with a specific focus on the context of the Pacific.

Table 2. Pros and Cons of Carbon Taxes

Carbon Taxes			
#	Pros +	#	Cons -
1.	More relevant for finance ministries (Parry et al., 2015).	1.	May not be ambitious enough.
2.	Simpler to implement as compared to emissions trading schemes.	2.	A punitive measure as compared to ETS that provides greater incentives.
3.	Provides certainty for business in terms of prices – helps companies plan.	3.	Targeted compensation from carbon tax revenues for low-income households in developing countries may be challenging as many citizens may not be formally registered taxpayers or benefit recipients (A. M. Bento, Jacobsen, & Liu, 2018).
4.	Generates revenue for governments.	4.	A carbon tax may not be palatable for PICs during the current record-high prices of fuel following the war on Ukraine.

5.	Parry (2015) argues that a benefit of carbon taxes over ETS is that carbon taxes allow revenue recycling where tax revenue could be redirected to citizens (especially in the form of dividends) to reduce the impact of carbon taxes on their cost of living.	5.	Due to the high fuel prices, most PICs have reduced or removed fuel excise taxes and as such a carbon tax would be inconsistent with these policies.
6.	Carbon taxes may be more suitable than an ETS due to their higher effectiveness in raising revenue and encouraging research, development and technology adoption.		

Table 3. Pros and Cons of Carbon Markets

Carbon markets			
#	Pros +	#	Cons -
1.	Provides more incentives to companies to reduce emissions and invest in “greener” technologies (carrot approach).	1.	More suited for Ministries of Climate Change (Parry et al., 2015).
2.	Opportunities for PICs to sell carbon credits to countries (such as Australia) or to voluntary carbon markets.	2.	Parry (2015) argues that ETS does nothing to improve distributional outcomes across households as it forgoes large economic efficiency gains from revenue recycling.
3.	Provides financial incentives to resource owners to conserve their resources instead of leasing/selling to developers.	3.	More complex in nature as compared to carbon taxes.
4.	Argued as having a greater potential to develop a vibrant green/blue economy in the Pacific.	4.	Requires greater resources and administrative support.
		5.	Carbon prices are volatile and make planning difficult for businesses.
		6.	Costs of accreditation for carbon abatement/sequestration projects are extremely high.

9.0 Recommendations

Based on our preliminary findings, we make the following recommendations:

1. PICs must evaluate their economies and map out their resources (human, technical and financial), legislative frameworks, administrative systems, data capturing and recording systems and their current progress in achieving their NDCs. This evaluation will inform the governments of PICs on the preferred carbon pricing pathway (carbon tax/carbon markets/or both) or whether carbon pricing, in all its various forms, is not relevant.
2. If a PIC is interested in carbon taxes, then the Singapore model could be a useful model to emulate. PICs can impose a very small carbon tax to firstly get their systems in order and to provide an initial signal to businesses. Governments should evaluate the impact of the initial carbon tax to determine whether the carbon tax is having its intended effect. A rigorous analysis should be conducted to determine the impact of the carbon tax on reducing GHG emissions, increase in prices and increased investment in renewable energy by companies. The focus of a carbon tax should not be on increasing revenue for the government. In fact, governments should recycle revenue either through citizen dividends to reduce the impact of price increases from carbon taxes or by reinvesting carbon tax revenue into projects that will reduce the country's carbon emissions. If the carbon price is low, then there should not be a significant increase in the prices of goods and services, but governments should monitor this to ensure that price gouging by companies is not taking place. Based on an initial analysis of carbon taxes on reducing carbon emissions and consultation with the private sector, governments can project how much carbon taxes need to be increased by each year in order to achieve NDC goals. If after the initial analysis, governments believe that a carbon tax has not achieved the desired outcomes, and that it is simply too burdensome on the country then governments should feel free to abandon a carbon tax.
3. If there is a general appetite for carbon taxes then a regional carbon tax could be considered.
4. It is extremely unlikely that a national ETS for a PIC would be successful given the complexity, high costs of administration and most importantly PICs are net producers of carbon credits (we absorb more carbon than we produce). Even if a regional carbon market was created, it cannot be just between SIDS of the Pacific. The supply of carbon credits would be greater than the demand and the price would be too low to justify the costs of establishing such as system. The most feasible approach would be to integrate with either an international ETS or to sell carbon credits to jurisdictions or to the voluntary carbon market.
5. Given Australia's recent commitment to creating an Indo-Pacific carbon offset market

and that Fiji and PNG were the first two official partners, this presents the best opportunity for PICs to take advantage of the surging demand for international, high quality, accredited carbon credits.

6. Identifying and accrediting carbon offset projects in the Pacific require necessary institutional and legislative frameworks. The Australian government has also pledged to assist PICs to develop their national climate policy frameworks and carbon accounting capacities. As these are very recent developments, there is still a lack of clarity on how this assistance will be provided or how PICs can access this support, but it is fair to surmise that PICs interested in selling carbon credits to this scheme must begin by conducting an internal analysis of the specific support and assistance required and be ready with these specific requests once details of the Indo-Pacific offset scheme gain greater clarity.
7. Given that the Pacific is still trying to recover from the economic impacts of COVID and the war on Russia, implementing carbon pricing at a national level may not be a priority. However, it is a priority at a global level and Pacific Island Countries, as the most vulnerable to climate change could use their position to advocate for higher carbon prices for the high-income and high emitting countries.

10.0 Conclusion

Carbon pricing is based on the economic philosophy that if carbon is not incorporated into the price of production, then companies will ignore the negative external impact of their operations on the environment. Putting a price on carbon thus creates a signal to the private sector to change their behaviour and divest from high carbon-emitting technologies and instead invest in innovations and practices that reduce carbon emissions. There are various forms of carbon pricing mechanisms that either emphasise a “stick” or “carrot” approach. Carbon taxes are more of a “stick approach” as a tax is imposed on a company’s carbon emissions. An ETS is more of a “carrot” approach as companies that are able to reduce their carbon emissions could generate revenue from selling carbon credits.

Based on our analysis, we found that stakeholders in the Pacific generally preferred ETSs as carbon pricing mechanisms. However, we suggest that PICs should not develop their own ETSs but instead identify and accredit carbon abatement/sequestration projects that can generate high quality, accredited carbon credits that can be sold to carbon markets. Recent developments, such as the growing demand for high-quality carbon credits and Australia’s Indo-Pacific Carbon Offset Scheme present opportunities for PICs.

Carbon pricing thus presents a number of opportunities for PICs to achieve their NDCs and potentially generate income. However, the choice of carbon pricing mechanism, whether a carbon tax, accessing carbon markets or a combination of both, ultimately depends on the individual circumstances of PICs.

GLOSSARY OF KEY TERMS

Cap and trade: The most popular form of an ETS where the government places a cap or quota on total allowable emissions in a jurisdiction. Entities that want to produce above their cap/quota must buy/trade carbon credits from other entities who have produced below their emissions cap.

Carbon pricing: the intentional factoring of the cost of emitting carbon into production/supply of a product/service

Carbon levy: Sometimes used interchangeably with carbon tax. The key difference is that a carbon levy is generally imposed by a specific sector rather than by a country.

Carbon tax: A mandatory national tax on carbon emissions.

Emissions trading scheme: A scheme where entities must purchase permits/allowances/credits in order to emit carbon and these are traded in a carbon market.

Emissions reductions fund: A fund established by the government that provides incentives to businesses to invest in carbon abatement/sequestration projects as the government will purchase carbon credits from registered projects.

Explicit carbon pricing: A form of carbon pricing where a carbon price is explicitly stated and is known ex-ante the implementation of the carbon policy.

Implicit carbon pricing: A form of carbon pricing where the carbon price is calculated ex-post a carbon policy is implemented.

Internal carbon pricing: A form of carbon pricing where carbon prices are not actual prices or costs incurred but are factored in the financial analysis of various capital investment projects.

Jurisdictional carbon market: A carbon market that is established for a national jurisdiction.

Voluntary carbon market: A carbon market where entities voluntarily participate in to trade carbon offsets.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: List of stakeholders consulted

#	Name	Organisation	Country/ Region Representing	Position
1.	Dr Peter Nuttall	Micronesian Center for Sustainable Transport (USP)	RMI/New Zealand/Fiji	Scientific and Technical Adviser
2.	Mr Vineil Narayan	United Nations Development Programme	Fiji	CRBE and BBB Project Manager - UNDP
3.	Mr Shelveen Kumar	Green Growth Institute (GGI)	Fiji	Climate Finance Advisor
4.	Mr Joel Abraham	Fiji Competition and Consumer Council (FCCC)	Fiji	CEO
5.	Professor Transform Aqorau	Solomon Islands National University (SINU)	Solomon Islands/Pacific	Professor of Ocean, Islands, and Sustainable Development
6.	Mr Sean Weaver	Ekos	New Zealand / Fiji	CEO
7.	Professor Andrew Macintosh	Australian National University	Australia	Professor of Environmental Law and Policy
8.	Professor Elisabeth Holland	The University of the South Pacific	Fiji/Pacific	Professor of the Ocean and Climate Change
9.	Dr Viliamu Iese	The University of the South Pacific	Fiji/Samoa/ Tuvalu/Pacific	Senior Lecturer – Disaster Risk Management
10.	Mr Aminisitai Delaisainai	United Nations Development Programme	Fiji	Risk Informed Development Financing Specialist
11.	Mr Sivendra Michael	United Nations Development Programme	Fiji	Programme Officer
12.	Mr Mohinesh Prasad	TotalEnergies Marketing (Fiji) Pte Ltd	Fiji/PNG/Pacific	Strategic Business Developer in South Pacific
13.	Professor Bronwyn Hayward	University of Canterbury	New Zealand	Professor of Political Science and International Relations
14.	Mr Garth Henderson	Ministry of Finance and Economic Management – Cook Islands	Cook Islands	Financial Secretary

#	Name	Organisation	Country/ Region Representing	Position
14.	Mr Garth Henderson	Ministry of Finance and Economic Management – Cook Islands	Cook Islands	Financial Secretary
15.	Mr Tristan Metcalfe	Ministry of Finance and Economic Management – Cook Islands	Cook Islands	Senior Macroeconomist
16.	Mr Joshua Mitchell	Ministry of Foreign Affairs & Immigration – Cook Islands	Cook Islands	Director, Treaties & Oceans Division
17.	Mr Nikhil Lal	Fiji Competition and Consumer Council (FCCC)	Fiji	Coordinator Operations
18.	Mr Ron Simpson	Regional Pacific NDC Hub	Fiji/Pacific	Regional Pacific NDC Hub Adaptation Advisor
19.	Mr Francis Mani	University of the South Pacific	Fiji	Senior Lecturer in Environmental Chemistry
20.	Mr Ravuni Uluilakeba	Korea International Cooperation Agency (KOICA)	Fiji	Project Manager – Renewable Energy Projects
21.	Mr Samuel Ieremia	Ministry of Finance – Government of Samoa	Samoa	Assistant Chief Executive Officer
22.	Mr Paul Roughan	Sky Island Initiative	Solomon Islands	Team Lead
23.	Mr Jamie Ovia	Tuvalu Climate Change Department	Tuvalu	Mitigation Policy Adviser

